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Trauma, Dystopia, and the Beast Within: A Study of William Golding's *Lord of the Flies*

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Abstract:

This paper examines William Golding's *Lord of the Flies* through the lens of trauma theory and the genre of dystopian literature. Written in the shadow of World War II and the Cold War, the novel reflects the psychological and societal breakdowns that result from trauma. Drawing on Golding's wartime experiences, the narrative portrays the descent into savagery among a group of boys stranded on a deserted island. This descent is analysed in the context of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), societal collapse, and the loss of innocence. Drawing on insights from trauma theory and dystopian scholarship, this study examines how the novel's dystopian vision functions as a warning against the more sinister dimensions of human nature. The work underscores the enduring impact of trauma on individuals and societies, making it a thought-provoking reflection of its time and a timeless exploration of humanity's dual capacity for creation and destruction.

Keywords: Trauma, Dystopia, Civilisation, Savagery, War, Psychological Disintegration.

Introduction

William Golding's *Lord of the Flies* offers a profound exploration of human nature, the breakdown of social order, and the psychological impact of trauma. Composed in the aftermath of the Second World War, the novel reflects the pervasive fear and existential uncertainty that marked the mid-twentieth century. In a 1962 interview, reflecting on *Lord of the Flies*, Golding remarked, "Look, you think you've been reading about little boys, but in fact you've been reading about the distresses and the wickedness of humanity" (Keating 194). Golding's viewpoint suggests that the roots of social disorder lie not in systems or institutions but in the fundamental imperfections of the individual. Under certain conditions, society not only fails to correct these flaws but may even intensify them—a belief that underpins the novel's dark vision of humanity.

Set on a remote island, the narrative follows a group of boys who attempt to establish a society but gradually descend into brutality. The island serves as a microcosm of the wider world, revealing how fear, the pursuit of power, and violence can overwhelm reason and morality. As Kinkead-Weekes and Gregor (1962) observe, "This is not a novel about children... the child world is only a microcosm of the adult world" (38), reinforcing the idea that the boys' moral failings are reflective of the society they come from.

The novel asserts that evil is not solely a product of flawed political or social systems but rather something more deeply embedded within human nature. Professor Lars Gyllensten echoes this idea in his Nobel Prize presentation, where he states that Golding "inveighs against those who think that it is the political or other systems that create evil. Evil springs from the depths of man himself ... it is the wickedness in human beings that creates the evil systems" ("Presentation Speech"). This insight strengthens the novel's core message: without moral discipline and societal boundaries, individuals are capable of extreme cruelty. The island

becomes a setting where this truth is exposed, as the boys' descent into brutality is driven not by their environment but by the darkness within themselves.

Golding's literary achievement lies in both his psychological insight and narrative mastery. As Peter (1957) observes, Golding "can be taken as a diagnostic example, reflecting the interests of our time" while also being "a good enough writer for a preoccupation with his work not to seem precious or misdirect" (581). Rich in symbolism, psychological complexity and narrative tension, Golding's *Lord of the Flies* explores the fine line between civilisation and savagery, exposing the inherent darkness at the heart of human nature.

By blending dystopian elements with psychological depth, Golding examines how fear and emotional trauma can lead to both personal and societal disintegration. This study will explore how the novel engages with its historical context, uses a dystopian framework, and draws upon trauma theory to present a lasting and unsettling reflection on the conflict between civilisation and barbarism in human nature.

Historical Context, War, and the Dystopian Lens

Lord of the Flies is shaped by the historical and philosophical anxieties of the mid-twentieth century. Golding's wartime experience as a naval officer deeply shaped his understanding of mankind's darker impulses and the instability of civilisation. Having witnessed the inhumanity and destruction of war, he came to see modern civilisation as morally unstable and fundamentally flawed. In an interview with James Baker (1982), Golding openly affirmed humanity as "a morally diseased creation" (134), highlighting the philosophical depth behind *Lord of the Flies*. Talon (1968) similarly describes Golding as "morally wounded by the extreme barbarity and sadism that the Second World War disclosed in the heart of supposedly civilised Man" and as someone who projected this unease into "a picture of children's hatred and deadly combats" (296). Hawlin (1995) supports this, stating that "Golding...is showing us

that the veneer of civilisation is very thin" (126), a view that underscores the novel's warning about the ease with which social order can disintegrate.

The novel reflects a sense of disillusionment through the recurring motif of war, which serves both as a backdrop and a catalyst for the boys' descent into savagery. Their very arrival on the island results from a wartime evacuation, and the plane crash leaves behind "a long scar smashed into the jungle" (Golding 11), symbolising how human violence taints even the most untouched natural environments. The arrival of the dead parachutist, a victim of the ongoing war, further blurs the line between the boys' inner fears and external realities. Mistaking the figure for the beast, they project their psychological terror onto it, avoiding the painful truth that the real danger lies within themselves. This projection of fear becomes a driving force in their collapse. As Paul Slayton (1993) argues, the novel is "a parable of the nuclear age," exposing how "society seems to have reached technological maturity while human morality is still prepubescent" (351). The contrast between progress and ethical decay lies at the heart of Golding's dystopian warning. Though the boys strive at first to construct a semblance of civilisation, it is soon undone by fear, rivalry and the resurgence of base human impulses. The island functions as a microcosm of global tensions, illustrating how swiftly order can collapse when individuals are isolated from the frameworks of structured society.

Golding's dystopia is not rooted in a distant future but in the present fears of post-war society. As İköz (2016) explains, dystopian literature often serves as a "warning," portraying "eerie worlds of the future" (10) where control replaces freedom. In this context, *Lord of the Flies* becomes a critique of human weakness and moral vulnerability. The title itself, a translation of the Hebrew *Beelzebub*, invokes decay and corruption. The pig's head on a stick—dubbed the 'Lord of the Flies'—symbolises the boys' loss of innocence and the rising bestiality among them. Simon, often viewed as the novel's moral centre, begins to understand this inner evil when he says haltingly, "What I mean is ... maybe it's only us" (Golding 111). Later, his

insight deepens as, whenever he thinks about the beast, “there rose before his inward sight the picture of a human at once heroic and sick” (Golding 128), highlighting the duality at the heart of human nature. These moments affirm Golding’s core belief: that evil is not an external monster but something rooted deep within the human psyche.

Hence, the battle between civilisation and chaos in the novel is not merely social—it reflects a profound existential crisis at the heart of humanity. Hobbes famously argued that without rules and authority, humans would revert to a state of war in which life would be “solitary, poore, nasty, brutish, and short” (89). Golding clearly aligns with this view. In *Lord of the Flies*, once the boys are freed from adult supervision and legal structures, they do not become noble savages—they descend into violence, cruelty, and superstition. The island becomes a stark symbol of what remains when civilisation is stripped away: raw human nature, untampered and destructive. As Siegl (1996) observes, “Golding argues that with the removal of civilisation follows the regression of certain human beings” (64). Johnson (2004) echoes this, noting that the novel reveals “the inevitability of gang savagery when individuals are placed outside societal controls” (99). Golding’s warning is clear—civilisation is a fragile and necessary restraint; without it, humanity teeters on the edge of chaos.

This is seen most clearly in the power struggle between Ralph and Jack. Ralph’s attempts to lead through order and cooperation gradually give way to Jack’s rise through fear and dominance. Carey (2009) interprets this shift as a reflection of historical cycles in which peace and democratic ideals are repeatedly threatened by violence and tyranny. The boys’ descent mirrors the broader historical failures of the twentieth century, suggesting that civilisation’s collapse is not a hypothetical outcome but a recurring human pattern.

Peter (1957) observes that Golding’s fiction challenges the ideal of progress and reveals “how easily order can fall apart” (582–3). War, both global and personal, becomes the lens through which Golding examines the human condition. Scholes and Rabkin point out that “the

utopian impulse has been largely replaced by dystopian projections of disastrous current trends" (174). *Lord of the Flies* is not simply a tale of survival—it is a dystopian meditation on the proximity of civilisation to chaos. It warns that the greatest threat to humanity is not external conflict but the internal forces of fear, power, and moral failure that reside within each of us.

Trauma and the Breakdown of Self and Society

In *Lord of the Flies*, William Golding shows how trauma affects both individuals and society. The story of a group of boys stranded on an island becomes a study of how fear, confusion, and violence can grow when people are cut off from order and safety. The emotional breakdown that follows their plane crash and isolation fits closely with trauma theory, particularly Cathy Caruth's view that trauma is not fully understood when it happens but returns in delayed and troubling ways—such as fear, memory gaps, and violent behaviour (153).

The boys' first instinct was to organize themselves into a structured community, complete with rules and designated roles, reflecting their desire to maintain the order of the world they left behind. This can be seen as a way of coping with the fear and uncertainty they feel. Nevertheless, their efforts to maintain order slowly fall apart. The fear of a 'beast' becomes a significant force in their world. Though the beast is not real, it represents the fear and darkness inside them. Simon realises this when he says the beast is "only us" (Golding 111). This matches Caruth's idea that trauma is internal and changes how we perceive reality.

In a broader context, the group's breakdown shows how trauma affects society. Their early attempts to hold meetings and use the conch to support fair discussion are replaced by fear and violence. Jack's rule, based on power and intimidation, takes over. The boys forget who they were as schoolchildren and become part of a savage tribe. Herman (1992) and Laub

(1995) argue that trauma breaks both the self and the social bond. On the island, these bonds are lost as the boys give in to fear and chaos.

Allen (1995) explains that trauma causes “overwhelming emotion and a feeling of utter helplessness” (14). This is reflected in the boys’ growing fear and their reactions to the imagined beast. Their fear becomes a shared belief that drives them further from reason and into barbarism. Jack uses this fear to take control, creating an illusion of safety while pushing the group towards violence. Piggy, who represents logic and intellect, holds on to the conch, a symbol of order. However, when both he and the conch are destroyed, it marks the end of reason and the rise of raw instinct.

In the early stages of the novel, Ralph symbolises structured leadership and the fading hope of preserving civilisation amid chaos. He is focused on keeping the signal fire burning, a symbol of rescue and connection to civilisation. Yet he struggles to articulate its importance—“The fire’s the most important thing on the island, because, because—” (Golding 175–6)—a hesitation that reflects his mounting stress and internal confusion. Though initially a symbol of order and rationality, Ralph is gradually drawn into the group’s descent into brutality, culminating in his involvement in Simon’s murder—an act that blurs the boundary between good and evil. As Rosenfield (1961) observes, “his body becomes the battleground where reason and instinct struggle, each to assert itself” (94). Ralph’s later admission—“That was Simon ... That was murder” (Golding 192–3)—marks a moment of painful self-awareness, revealing both his guilt and his recognition of the group’s moral collapse, as well as his susceptibility to it. Golding’s depiction of Ralph’s grief highlights the broader psychological impact of trauma—not only does it fracture the individual’s sense of identity, but it also profoundly alters their perception of humanity and the world around them.

In Golding’s novel, trauma operates on two levels—it disturbs the inner psyche through fear and guilt, and simultaneously undermines the structures essential for social order. Golding

uses the boys' descent into brutality to reflect the dehumanising effects of real-world catastrophes, particularly the horrors witnessed during war. *Lord of the Flies* transcends a mere tale of survival; it stands as a stark warning about the profound and enduring impact of trauma on both the individual psyche and the fabric of society.

Symbols of Civilization and Their Destruction

In the novel, Golding employs powerful symbols to illustrate the alarming ease with which human society can disintegrate. These symbols reflect key parts of civilised life—order, reason, hope—and how they are gradually lost. As Michel-Michot (1990) notes, “Golding works out his themes employing symbolism” (82). The destruction of these symbols mirrors the boys' descent into savagery and the loss of moral structure.

The title *Lord of the Flies* stands as a powerful and disturbing symbol of the innate savagery and moral collapse within human nature. Its name, derived from the Hebrew *Ba'alzevuv*—translated as *Beelzebub*, a name for the Devil—evokes images of decay, destruction, and demoralisation, mirroring Freud's concept of the Id: the primitive, instinctual force that operates beneath the surface of civilisation. This force is made horrifyingly visible in the brutal killing of the sow, where “the sow fell and the hunters hurled themselves at her... the air was full of sweat and noise and blood and terror.” The violence is relentless, as “Jack was on top of the sow, stabbing downward with his knife,” while “Roger found a lodgement for his point and began to push till he was leaning with his whole weight.” Their complete abandonment to cruelty marks a turning point in the boys' descent. When the sow finally collapses, “they were heavy and fulfilled upon her,” signifying not victory, but a loss of innocence. The pig's severed head, mounted on a stick sharpened at both ends, becomes a grim offering to the imagined Beast, its “spilled guts” swarmed by flies (Golding 167-9). This grotesque idol, the Lord of the Flies, represents the fear and darkness festering within the boys

themselves. To Simon, the only character with a deeper moral insight, the head reveals the truth: “I’m part of you... I’m the reason why it’s no go” (Golding 177). His confrontation with this inner evil, culminating in the “blackness within” that engulfs him, underscores Golding’s haunting message—that the real beast is not external, but resides within the human soul.

The beast is one of the novel’s most haunting and evolving symbols, representing the primal fear and inner darkness within the boys. Though it begins as an imagined threat—a “snake-thing” feared by the littluns—it soon becomes a powerful psychological force that drives the group’s descent into savagery. The dead parachutist, mistaken for the beast, reveals how fear distorts reality, turning a symbol of adult conflict into a monstrous myth. As fear grows, it becomes a social weapon; Jack exploits the beast to manipulate the boys, positioning himself as their protector while justifying violence and authoritarian rule. Only Simon understands the truth: “Maybe there is a beast... maybe it’s only us” (Golding 111) recognising that the real horror lies not in an external creature, but in the human capacity for evil. Tragically, his insight is lost in the chaos, as the boys kill him in a blind frenzy—consumed by the very fear they created.

The conch shell symbolises authority, order, and civilised discourse. From the beginning, it unites the boys and gives structure to their meetings, granting the power to speak during assembly and also the power of speech, an ability that separates humans from animals. Its connection to Piggy, the most rational character, links it to logic and social stability. Ralph, who believes in rules and cooperation, uses the conch to lead. However, as fear and division grow, its influence wanes—culminating in Jack’s dismissal, “And the conch doesn’t count at this end of the island--” (Golding 186) which signals a shift towards savagery. The symbolic collapse is complete when Roger kills Piggy and shatters the conch. Golding describes: “The rock struck Piggy a glancing blow from chin to knee; the conch exploded into a thousand white fragments and ceased to exist... the body of Piggy was gone” (222–23). This moment marks

the destruction of reason and the triumph of violence, underscoring the novel's warning about the fragility of civilisation.

Piggy's glasses, used to light the fire, symbolise knowledge, clarity, and human invention. Closely tied to his role as the voice of reason and intellect, the glasses represent not only his literal vision but also insight, education, and rational thought—qualities the boys gradually abandon. Their practical use in starting the signal fire, a symbol of hope and civilisation, links them to mankind's ability to harness nature through science. However, as savagery grows, the glasses are valued not for what they represent but for their utility, becoming a tool of control. When Jack's tribe steals them, it is a symbolic theft of reason and cooperation, marking the group's descent into fear and power-driven chaos. The final blow comes when Roger kills Piggy and the glasses shatter, destroying the last vestiges of logic and hope. With nothing left—no fire, no vision, no authority—Ralph is powerless, and the island is plunged fully into disorder.

Fire is a complex, evolving symbol that shifts from representing hope and civilisation to embodying chaos and destruction. Initially, the signal fire reflects the boys' desire for rescue and their connection to order—Ralph's insistence on keeping it lit signifies responsibility, cooperation, and moral clarity. As the boys grow more savage, however, the fire is neglected, symbolising their abandonment of long-term goals and societal values. Jack and the hunters prioritise hunting over maintaining the fire, and eventually, fire becomes a weapon used to hunt Ralph, not a means of survival. Golding captures this shift with violent imagery: "Suddenly he (Ralph) blundered into the open, found himself again in that open space--and there was the fathom-wide grin of the skull, no longer ridiculing a deep blue patch of sky but jeering up into a blanket of smoke. Then Ralph was running beneath trees, with the grumble of the forest explained. They had smoked him out and set the island on fire" (Golding 242). Ironically, this final inferno—born not of reason but of brutality—leads to their rescue, as the smoke attracts

a naval officer. The fire's transformation from a civilising force to a symbol of savagery underscores Golding's grim warning about the fragility of human society and how easily progress can descend into ruin.

A lesser-discussed but equally important symbol is the dead parachutist, which arrives on the island just after Ralph, Piggy, and Simon wish for a sign from the adult world: "If only they could send us something grown-up... a sign or something" (Golding 117). The parachutist, intended as a message from the adult world, becomes a symbol of its brutality. Rather than wisdom or guidance, the boys receive a corpse—war-ravaged and lifeless—representing the inhumanity of the world they once idealised.

Simon's death is the darkest and most symbolic moment in the novel, blurring the line between sacred sacrifice and collective guilt. Spangler (1964) highlights this duality, noting that "Simon is made a scapegoat, the capital-punishment of whom satisfies the established state (the tribe) by eliminating a supposed enemy" (221). Believing they are killing the beast, the boys justify their violence; later, they recognise it is Simon but continue to rationalise the act as necessary. His death turns him into a martyr, symbolising the destruction of spiritual truth and moral conscience. In their frenzied ritual, the boys become celebrants in a sacrificial rite, illustrating how fear can drive collective violence. Cox (1985) describes the moment as revealing "the power of original sin" (115), exposing the innate savagery within them. Their descent continues as "Piggy is murdered...and Ralph is hunted...like the pigs they are accustomed to kill" (Peter 582) until a naval officer intervenes. These acts signal not only the loss of innocence but also the collapse of all moral and spiritual order on the island.

The appearance of butterflies during the novel's most haunting scenes symbolises innocence and the indifference of nature to human cruelty. As the boys violently kill the sow, "bright flowers grew and butterflies danced round each other" (Golding 167) a peaceful image starkly contrasted with the chaos of blood and terror, highlighting how far they've fallen from

innocence. Later, after Simon's brutal death, his body is gently taken by the sea, "surrounded by a fringe of inquisitive bright creatures" (Golding 190) evoking a quiet, almost sacred farewell. In these moments, the butterflies serve as a powerful reminder of the fragile beauty and purity that endure briefly amid overwhelming savagery.

The destruction of these symbols reflects the broader context of World War II. The war, like the story, was a time when technology and science advanced, but moral values declined. The atomic bomb, a symbol of human progress, also brought massive destruction. Ultimately, the novel's symbols serve as a poignant reminder of the fragility of human civilisation. When core values such as reason, respect and compassion are abandoned, the descent into chaos becomes inevitable. Golding's message is clear: without conscience, civilisation will collapse under its weight.

The Cyclical Nature of Violence and a Glimmer of Hope

The ending of *Lord of the Flies* does not provide a clear solution but offers a powerful reflection on the cycle of violence and the darker side of human nature. The boys' "rescue" by a naval officer seems, at first, like a moment of salvation. However, the irony is evident—they are not returning to peace but to a world already consumed by war. The officer's uniform and warship remind us that the moral collapse seen on the island is not unusual; it mirrors the violence of the adult world. As Van Vuuren (2004) explains, "The adult world can offer no salvation, but only further destruction on a much larger scale" (20).

Peter (1957) notes that the boys are "instantly reduced to a group of painted urchins," but their return to childhood cannot erase "the knowledge of what they have done and meant to do" (582). This final moment supports Golding's key message: that evil does not come from outside forces—it already exists within every person and surfaces when the time is ripe.

The officer's reaction reveals how little he truly understands the boys' ordeal. His casual, almost mocking tone—"We saw your smoke. What have you been doing? Having a war or something?" (Golding 288)—fails to grasp the depth of their trauma. The irony lies in the fact that he is part of a much larger war, engaged in the very same violence and destruction that the boys have mirrored on the island. His arrival is not a moment of actual rescue but a stark reminder that the moral failures seen in the boys are reflections of the adult world.

Nevertheless, Golding offers a small sense of hope. Ralph's tears—"for the end of innocence, the darkness of man's heart" (Golding 248)—show that he understands what has happened. It is a moment of catharsis and moral awareness. Ralph never fully gives in to the loss of civility. He values rules, fairness, and cooperation, as shown when he says, "the rules are the only thing we've got" (Golding 114). Even as order collapses, he tries to hold on to what is right.

Piggy and Simon also stand for reason and kindness. They support fairness and try to keep the group focused on rescue and unity. Their use of the conch for fair discussion shows their respect for order and shared values. Even Jack, early on, says, "We've got to have rules and obey them. After all, we're not savages" (Golding 55)—though he later abandons this belief. These small moments suggest that the values of civilisation do not disappear completely, even when fear and power take control.

Golding's view of human nature is dark but not without hope. He suggests that people are capable of both destruction and choosing between right and wrong. Characters like Ralph, Piggy and Simon reflect the enduring human impulse to act ethically, even amid chaos and despair. This idea reflects existential and psychological theories that say recognising both good and evil within ourselves is the first step to change.

Although the boys leave the island, the questions raised by their experience remain. *Lord of the Flies* both criticises violence and suggests that moral growth is possible—if people are willing to face the truth about themselves.

Conclusion

William Golding's *Lord of the Flies* weaves together historical context, trauma theory and dystopian thought to interrogate the inherent fragility of civilised society. Emerging from the ruins of World War II, the novel captures a world reeling from brutality and casts doubt on mankind's ability to evolve through suffering. The boys' descent into savagery, shaped by fear and trauma, shows how easily order can collapse when psychological wounds go unhealed and power is left unchecked.

Golding uses clear symbols to represent logic, structure, and hope. As these are damaged or destroyed, the boys lose their grip on reason and fall into chaos. The destruction of these symbols mirrors their loss of control and the rise of violence. However, there is a moment of reflection at the end. Ralph's tears for "the end of innocence" and "the darkness of man's heart" (Golding 248) show that understanding and regret are still possible. His sorrow offers a faint chance of redemption through self-awareness.

Lord of the Flies is both a product of its time and a lasting message. It not only reflects post-war fears but also speaks to any age where conflict, fear, and moral failure threaten society. Through his harrowing tale, Golding urges readers to reflect on the shadows within human nature and to ask whether civilisation can ever escape its self-destructive tendencies.

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